

LEVEL OF GASTRONOMIC TOURISM IN UZBEKISTAN

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Annotation. This article shows the importance of gastronomic tourism, its place in the tourism infrastructure today, the share of income from this sector in our economy, at the same time, the high level of gastronomic tourism in the Republic of Uzbekistan is shown, it is shown on the example of each province, and the differences and connections between the provinces are analyzed. Several proposals for the development of gastronomic tourism have been made.

Key words: gastronomy, food, drinks, kitchen, restaurant, tourism, region, tourist, food, cook.

INTRODUCTION. The ultimate goal of the large-scale reforms implemented in all spheres today is to further develop the economy of our country and serve to improve the well-being of our people. In this regard, the tourism sector also plays an important role. As the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev Miromonovich noted: "Tourism is one of the important sectors of the economy. It is necessary to further improve this network with the effective use of existing opportunities, which is required by the times itself" [1]. In order to develop tourism at a high level, it is first necessary to increase attention to its most important branches. Today, gastronomic tourism is recognized as one of the main types of tourism in many developed countries of the world.

Gastronomic tourism is the travel of a person or community to taste, enjoy or heal from national foods and drinks, as well as the methods of production of these products, culinary secrets, mastering of cooking technologies, specific characteristics and history of the origin of food. means visiting from one region to another region or from one country to another country in order to get to know.

Any tourist, whether he wants it or not, is directly connected with food and drinks for daily needs. Based on this, we have to divide the tourists into two gastronomic types:

- in the first round, tourists organize a direct gastronomic tourism trip;
Gastronomic travel - in which the traveler interprets the concept of this or that

country, learns about the psyche of the people of this country and gets information about its mentality through national food [2].

- in the second round, the purpose of the visitor may be different, for example: a sports competition, visiting holy places, trade cooperation, etc., but the visitor does not avoid gastronomic tourism. Today, attention to gastronomic tourism creates a basis for the development of other types of tourism.

Every person whose professional activity is serving tourists, as well as professionals who are directly related to the reception of non-tourist guests from different countries, are hospitality related to the food culture and traditions of the peoples of the world. requires that they know the laws of the state. This allows restaurant and hotel service professionals to make the right decisions and not make mistakes when accommodating foreign guests and organizing their meals, not only foreign guests, but also local guests feel comfortable in this area. This process has a unique appearance in Uzbekistan.

According to the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan on October 10, 2012 "On improving the activities of public catering organizations and increasing the qualifications of employees"[3], the National Culinary Art International Center was established under the Union of Chefs of Uzbekistan. With this decision, its authority was expanded and strengthened. The existence of long-standing traditions and the variety of national dishes lead to the wide popularity of Uzbek cuisine in foreign countries, reflected in this document. In this regard, many decisions and decrees have been announced and projects are being created. "Food tourism is growing around the world for two main reasons: firstly, the desire of people to know where their food comes from, and secondly, the desire to discover new food and cooking"[4] . Food tourism based on local and regional gastronomy can play an important role in the development of small and medium-sized businesses as an element of economic growth, because, in addition to tourist activity, gastronomic tourism is also important for the foreign trade turnover of countries and the expansion of business relations of enterprises. Historically, spices, wine, fruits and other foodstuffs have often been used as currency[5].

If we calculate without taking into account the trade turnover, today's food expenses of tourists in gastronomic tourism itself make up 30-40%. Currently, it is popular among tourists to buy food and drinks as souvenirs for those aged 30 and over, considering that 95% of tourists are aged 30 and over, we observe that the main gift of tourists is gastronomic products. will be possible.

Years	Number of tourists	Average income (\$)	Income from gastronomic tourism (\$)
2017 yil	2,7 million	823500000	288225000
2018 yil	5,4 million	1647000000	576450000
2019 yil	6,4 million	1952000000	683200000
2020 yil	1,5 million	457500000	160125000
2021 yil	1,8 million	549000000	192150000
2022 yil	4,5 million	1372500000	480375000

1-table [6]

Our national dishes and drinks, which are long-established, ecologically clean and invigorating for the human body, are very popular. Now, through these unique national dishes, it is possible to connect gastronomic tourism with rural tourism. In fact, in the villages located in the regions, there are national dishes unique to that place, the taste and composition of which cannot be repeated in the villages of other regions. It is precisely in this aspect that such dishes are considered delicious for foreign tourists and local residents[7]. Our country has all the foods and drinks that are suitable for the four seasons of the year, have their own ancient history, and are also necessary for human life, for example, radish snack with cream in spring, shawul soup, sumalak , halim, blue dumplings, blue somsa, kovatok pilaf (vine soup), fried cauliflower, and moshkhor with mint are eaten. In the summer, tomato kebab, stuffed cabbage, dumbell soup, stuffed pepper, lagmon, yogurt soup, vegetable snack, chalop, goja soup, steamed kebab, meat dimples, vegetable dimples. , buttermilk, hot tea, fruit compotes, etc. are welcome. In autumn, fried fish, lakka kebab, barra meat, head soup, quail kebab, behili pilaf, potato manti, honey quince, cut lagman, pumpkin somsa are not absent from the tables. On frosty days, gazi-karta, podstumba, mutton fat pilaf, kart-dumba pilaf, gazi pilaf, barra kebab, radish salad, fried soup, moshkichiri, fruits stored for the winter, their jam, compote, pickles, vinegar and pickled vegetables are eaten[8].

But it is natural that the dishes of different nationalities and peoples living in the same region are similar to each other. For example, if we look at the Uzbek cuisine, then along with our national dishes, there are dozens of dishes from Russian, Ukrainian, Caucasian, Mongolian, Tatar, Tajik, Kazakh, Uyghur, Italian and other nations. We can observe that it is getting better and better.

Its popularity today is influenced by a number of factors:

- currently the need for food is the primary physiological need of a person;
- increase in the income of the population and increase in the prices of food and recreation;
- the main service sector of the food tourism and hospitality industry;
- popularity of healthy food and organic products;

CONCLUSION.

As can be seen from the information in this table, the number of food establishments in relation to the population of the Republic is different, and in some regions there are more than the population: Tashkent city, Navoi region, Tashkent region, Bukhara region. It is less in some regions: regions like Andijan, Kashkadarya, Surkhandarya, Namangan. The minimum population is 829.9 people, the maximum is 4190.3 people, and the difference between them is 5 times.

I think that it would also be appropriate if, taking into account a certain distance on the basis of the map, food stalls were established in all distant and nearby regions of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

As a result of the research, we were convinced that our chefs who serve in many kitchens in Uzbekistan have practical skills in the field of cooking, and if they organize scientific training, then our various Uzbek dishes will be known.

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